

**PEIERLS BARRIER - NABARRO AND MIGRATION MONOVACANCIES AND MULTIVACANCIES
IN GRAPHENE**

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Abstract

In the article, we compare a graphene monolayer with the Peierls–Nabarro barrier, which is equal to the force of interatomic interaction. This barrier is calculated from the formation energy of monovacancies, divacancies and other structural defects and the length of the newly formed carbon bond. It is shown that the Peierls–Nabarro barrier is maximum for a monovacancy and then decreases for complex defects.

Keywords: graphene, monolayer, monovacancy, divacancy, defect, carbon, barrier, dislocation.

Introduction

Defects and impurities have a significant impact on the mechanical, electrical, optical and other properties of solids, and, in particular, graphene, discovered at the beginning of the 21st century [1]. Graphene has two types of defects: (i) natural defects known as intrinsic defects in graphene, such as Stone–Wells defects, single vacancy defects, multiple defects, linear defects, and carbon adatoms; and (ii) physically introduced defects, known as extrinsic defects in graphene, which are foreign adatoms and foreign impurities [2-4].

In this article, we will consider the effect of monovacancies and multivacancies on the physical properties of graphene. Then we compare the energy of their formation and migration with the Peierls–Nabarro barrier in graphene.

Monovacancy in graphene

A monovacancy (SV) or Schottky defect is the absence of an atom or ion at a site in a crystal lattice. A monovacancy (SV) was experimentally observed in graphene in [4-7] and its image is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Monovacancy in graphene: experimental TEM image (a); atomic structure obtained as a result of calculations using the DFT method (b) [4].

Calculations have shown that the local threefold symmetry of graphene D_{3h} is broken to the C_{2v} symmetry due to the Jahn-Teller distortion [8-11]. A monovacancy has a 5/9 structure, where a new bond with length b_{CV} arises between a pair of three atoms with dangling bonds, forming a pentagon with a displacement d_{CV} of the third atom from the graphene plane [2, 12-14]. This moment is depicted in Figure 2. The energy of formation of monovacancies is $E_{CV} = 7.6-7.9$ eV and the length of the newly formed bond is $b_{CV} =$

$0.18 - 0.2$ nm, the migration barrier is $\Delta E_{CV} = 1.3$ eV at $100 - 200$ °C and out-of-plane movement $d_{CV} = 0.018$ nm [4, 8-10]. If we take the average values of E_{CV} , ΔE_{CV} and energy converted into joules, we get $E_{CV} = 12.4 \cdot 10^{-19}$ N/m, $\Delta E_{CV} = 2.1 \cdot 10^{-19}$ J = $2.1 \cdot 10^{-19}$ N/m. The force of formation of monovacancies is equal to $F_{CV} = E_{CV}/b_{CV} = 12.4 \cdot 10^{-19}$ N/m/ $1.9 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m = $6.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N, The force of movement of the migration barrier is equal to $\Delta F_{CV} = \Delta E_{CV}/d_{CV} = 2.1 \cdot 10^{-19}$ N/m/ $0.18 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m = $11.7 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N.

Figure 2. Initial ground state (a), transition state (b) and final ground state (c) for one step of migration of a reconstructed 5/9 monovacancy into graphene [2].

Divacancy in graphene

A double vacancy (DV) means either the fusion of two single vacancies (SV) or the removal of two adjacent carbon atoms. The DV can be reconstructed to produce two pentagons and one octagon, indicated by the 5-8-5 defect [15, 16]. Figure 3 shows the atomic structure of divacancies obtained by DFT and experimental images obtained by TEM.

The formation energy of DV is equal to $E_{DV} = 7.5$ eV and is less than that of SV, the length of the newly formed bond is $b_{DV} = 0.17$ nm. The transformation barrier values for the transition $5-8-5 \rightarrow 555-777$ are 5.17 - 5.27 eV [8, 9]. All three divacancy states are stable at room temperature.

Figure 3. Divacancy in graphene. Atomic structures obtained from DFT calculations (a-c). Experimental TEM images corresponding to atomic models (d-f). Here defect 5-8-5 (a, d), defect 555-777 (b, e) defect 5555-6-7777. (c, f) [4].

The DV defect is caused by a dangling bond, whereas the 5-8-5 defect causes only local deformations. Being a saturated eight-membered ring compound, the cyclooctane (CH_2)₈ molecule also has a non-planar structure, resembling a crown or a boat. Since

defect 5-8-5 also has significant local curvature, the system is replaced with defect 555-777 or 5555-6-7777 to reduce local curvature. Three different reconstructed states of divacancy in graphene are usually observed in it under electron irradiation (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the structure and energetics of three divacancy states in graphene: the $V_2(5-8-5)$ state, the $V_2(555-777)$ state, and the $V_2(5555-6-7777)$ state and the transition states for the transition between the V_2 (states 5-8-5) and $V_2(555-777)$ and between the states $V_2(555-777)$ and $V_2(5555-6-7777)$ [2].

Multivacancies in graphene

The removal of more than two carbon atoms, known as multiple defects or multivacancies, can result in a larger, more complex defect. In this regard, one would expect to observe a more or less random selection of vacancies. Therefore, local rearrangement of the lattice around multivacancies and the formation of a random set of non-hexagonal polygons is possible. Two pentagons and one octagon appear for the reconstructed double vacancy, resulting in the absence of dangling bonds [17]. Multivacancies can be created by modern physical and chemical methods [18-21]. Research results show that multivacancies are more easily formed than monovacancies under electron irradiation [22]. Calculations show that the energy of formation of multivacancies in graphene and carbon nanotubes is significantly lower than the energy of formation of monovacancies [23-26]. The formation energy of the 5555-6-7777 defect is between 5-8-5 and 555-777 (Fig. 4) and is about 6 eV with a bond length of about 0.23 nm [27, 28].

Peierls-Nabarro barrier

In [29], our proposed model of the surface layer of atomically smooth metals is generalized. To determine the thickness of the surface layer of various compounds, the size dependence of the melting temperature $T_m(r)$ was used:

$$\begin{aligned} T_m(r) &= T_m(\infty) \cdot (1 - R(I)/r), & r \gg R(I), \\ T_m(r) &= T_m(\infty) \cdot (1 - R(I)/(R(I) + r)), & R(0) \leq r \leq R(I). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here the first formula coincides with the formula of R. Tolman [30], where $R(I) = 2\delta$, δ is the Tolman parameter, which is not determined experimentally. The second formula is further defined in the region $R(0) < r < R(I)$, so that when $r = 0$ the first formula does not go to infinity. The parameter $R(I)$ is related to the surface energy γ by the formula [29]:

$$R(I) = 2\gamma\nu/RT. \quad (2)$$

Here γ is the surface energy of the massive sample; ν – volume of one mole; R – gas constant; T – temperature. In [31] it is shown that, with an accuracy of 3%, the following is true:

$$\gamma = 0,70 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (3)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the solid (K). The relationship holds for all metals and for other crystalline compounds. At $T = T_m$ from (2) we obtain:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu \text{ (m)}. \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) shows that the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ is determined by one parameter – the molar (atomic) volume of the element ($\nu = M/\rho$, M – molar mass (kg/mol), ρ – density (kg/m³)), which changes periodically in accordance with table D.I. Mendeleev.

We compare the $R(I)$ monolayer with the Peierls-Nabarro barrier, which is equal to the force of interatomic interaction [32, 33]. In contrast to the Frenkel-Kontorova model [34], as well as works [35, 36] and others, we will propose a model that can be used to estimate the barrier $F(I)_{P-N}$ and voltage $\sigma(I)_{P-N}$ the Peierls – Nabarro:

$$\begin{aligned} F(I)_{P-N} &= \gamma \cdot R(I)/n = \gamma \cdot a, \\ \sigma(I)_{P-N} &= F(I)_{P-N}/S = \gamma/a = E \cdot \varepsilon(I), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where n is the number of layers in layer $R(I)$; a is the lattice constant; S – barrier area (a^2), $\sigma(I)_{P-N}$ – Peierls-Nabarro stress; E – Young's modulus; ε represents the relative elongation of the lattice parameter in the direction of the external force F . In the case of graphene, $R(I) = a = 0.246$ nm, $n = 1$, $\gamma = 3157$ mJ/m².

Peierls-Nabarro barrier and parameters of vacancies in graphene

Using equations (1) – (5), we calculate the energy parameters of graphene and vacancies in graphene (Table 1).

Table 1.

Parameters of graphene and vacancies in graphene

Parameter	$F(I)_{P-N}$, 10^{-9} N	$\sigma(I)_{P-N}$, MPa	F_{CV} , 10^{-9} N	$\sigma(I)_{CV}$, MPa	F_{DV} , 10^{-9} N	$\sigma(I)_{DV}$, MPa	F_D , 10^{-9} N	$\sigma(I)_D$, MPa
Graphene	0,26	4268	-	-	-	-	-	-
Monovacancy	-	-	0,65	36111	-	-	-	-
Divacancy	-	-	-	-	0,44	25872	-	-
Defect 5555-6-7777	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,26	11304

From Table 1 it follows that the Peierls–Nabarro stress for pure graphene is $\sigma(I)_{P-N} = 4.3$ GPa and then decreases with increasing number of defects. This value of the Peierls–Nabarro stress leads to warping of sheets of pure graphene [2, 37]. In graphene, the deformation $\sigma(I)$ of the quasi-two-dimensional lattice created by the defects listed above can induce strong pseudomagnetic fields, promote the appearance of new Landau levels and paramagnetic centers, and have a significant impact on the electronic characteristics [38–43]. From Table 1 it follows that the Peierls–Nabarro barrier for pure graphene is $F(I)_{PN} = 0.26 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N, and for typical steel $F(I)_{PN} = 0.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N. A monovacancy has a large Peierls barrier – Nabarro, although they are not easy to form. The Peierls–Nabarro barrier inhibits the movement of dislocations in metals and leads to its strengthening [44]. Defects in graphene, which can inhibit the movement of dislocations, are more easily formed under electron irradiation [22].

The displacement of monovacancies outside the graphene plane is (see above) $d_{CV} = 0.018$ nm and, therefore, $d_{DV} = 0.027$ nm and $d_D = 0.046$ nm (see Table 1). In [45], the formation and movement of dislocations in graphene was studied in real time using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy. It was established in [45] that the source of dislocations in graphene are the so-called Stone–Wales defects, which are formed as a result of rotation of the C–C bond through an angle of 90° , as a result of which two pentagons and two heptagons appear in the hexagonal lattice. Dislocations move by sliding or crawling at a speed of ~ 0.1 nm/min. Each dislocation creates a deformation field in its vicinity, which extends over ~ 1 nm.

Conclusion

Today, there are several mechanisms of dislocation braking, which can be divided into two groups. The first group discusses the inhibition of dislocations due to the presence of potential barriers in crystals caused by various structural defects, including the Peierls–Nabarro barrier. The second group discusses the inhibition of dislocations due to the presence of dynamic interaction in crystals. This includes interaction with electrons, phonons, excitons, magnons and other elementary excitations of the crystal lattice. The role of the latter excitations is insignificant for most crystals, but the interaction with phonons is most significant. As we have shown, the Peierls–Nabarro barrier in graphene is maximum for a monovacancy.

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